

Science

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF EK-KUSHTA (PSORIASIS)-A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Psoriasis is described in Ayurveda as *ek-kushta*, it is type of *kshudrakushta*. The number of people suffering from Psoriasis all over the world is increasing progressively. Ayurvedic medicine is oriented toward prevention, health maintenance and treatment of diseases. There is large number of drugs of herbal and mineral origin mentioned in Ayurvedic texts, regarding the treatment of *ek-kushta*. The present case study is successful Ayurvedic management of a case of *ek-kushta* (psoriasis). Here a case report of a 35 years-male having with the complaint of *ubhay pad pradeshi twak aaraktavarniya twakavaivarnya, kandu, twakrukshata* etc. since 2 months. He was treated with Ayurvedic herbs & some *panchkarma* procedure which give effective result with Ayurvedic Management.

Keywords: Psoriasis; Ek-Kushta; Ayurvedic Herbs; Effective Therapy.

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1. Introduction

Ek-kushta is one of the skin disorder explained by Acharya in *kushta-chikitsa adhyaya*. There are two types of *kushta*, namely *mahakushta* and *kshudrakushta*. *Ek-kushta* is one of *kshudra-kushta*. *Aswdanam* (not perspire), *mahavastu* (extensive) and *yana-masyoshakalopamam* (looks like fish scale), *arun varna* (discoloration) are the main symptoms *ek-kushta*⁽¹⁾. *Ek-kushta* is most closely resembles like Psoriasis. Psoriasis is a long-lasting autoimmune disease characterized by patches of abnormal skin. These skin patches are typically red, dry, itchy and scaly. Psoriasis varies in severity from small, localized patches to complete body coverage⁽²⁾.

In modern era, different types of pollution, lack of proper diet, uses of various cosmetic, chemicals all this leads prevalence of skin diseases day by day. The prevalence rate of psoriasis is 0.44-2.8%

in India⁽³⁾. Line of Ayurvedic treatment for psoriasis is *shodhan* and *shaman chikitsa*. *Shodhan chikitsa* can be given by *vaman* (emesis) and *virechana* (purgation)

Raktamokshana (blood-letting) whenever Vata is dominant, *Ghrita* should be prescribed, similarly, where the *Kapha* is dominant, *Vamana Karma* & in the dominancy of *Pitta*, *Virechana Karma* & *Raktamokshana* should be done⁽⁴⁾. While *Shaman chikitsa* given by internal and external medication. all the medicine which are used having properties *tikta* and *katu rasatamak* which is used to purification of vat, *kaph* and *rakta Dosha*. *Ek-kushta* can be treated remarkably with procedures of *panchakarma* and internal medications. By this treatment it gives excellent result to patient.

2. Case Report

A 35 years old male patient came to us with following chief complaint –

Table 1 : Showing symptoms & duration of patient:

No.	CHIEF COMPLAINTS	Duration
	<i>Ubhay pad & padtal pradeshi</i>	} 2 months
	1) <i>twakvaivarnya</i> (discolouration)	
	2) <i>Yanamasyoshaklopamam</i> (erythematous patches rounded and irregular shape appearing as silvery scale)	
	3) <i>Kandu</i> (itching)	
	4) <i>twakrukshata</i> (dryness)	

History of Present Illness

A 35 years old male patient presented with reddish erythromatous plague on legs he was complaining of itching and burning sensation over there.

On history patient had above complaints since 2 months. Patient took modern medicine but get only temporary symptomatic relief. Severity of symptoms increased day by days, So he came for our clinic for Ayurvedic treatment

Past History

No any H/o

- DM / Hypertension / Thyroid disorder
- TRAUMA
- Addiction
- Family illness (kulvrutta –
- matrukul - sandhigata vata,
- pitrukul - madhumeha,
- swakul - Prakrut)

Astavidha Pariksha

- *Nadi* (pulse) = 78/min.
- *Mala* (stool) = awastambha
- *Mutra* (urine) = 3-4 times in a day

- *Jeeva* (tounge) = Eshat saam.
- *Agni* = prakrut
- *Shabda* (speech) = Normal.
- *Akruti* = Madhyama.
- *Bala* = Madhyama.
- *Raktadaaba* (B.P) = 120/70 mm/Hg.

Investigation

Table 2: Showing investigations done for study

CBC	HB- 12 gm%	WBC- 6700	• PLATELET - 184000
ESR- 18 mm	(westerngreen method)		
BSL (Radam)-	Within normal	Limit	
URINE (R) -	81 mg/dl		

3. Materials and Methods

- **Method of sampling-** simple randomized
- **Study design:** experimental clinical single case study.

Materials

Table 3: Showing material used in study

No.	Dravya	Dose	Duration	Anupan
1	Ras manikya	125mg	Bd after meal	
2	talsindur	125 mg	Bd after meal	
3	Praval panchamrut	500mg	1Bd after meal	With luke warm water
4	Kaishor gugul	250mg	1Bd after meal	
5	Nimba-patol- katukrohinyadi kwath	10ml	With half cup of water after meal	
6	Kamdudha rasa	250mg	1Bd after meal	

Table 4: Showing panchakarma done in study

No.	procedure	duration
1	Virechana –by 5gm trivruttavaleha with luke warm	daily at night
2	Stanik abhyang (ubhay pad pradeshi) with Valyapladi oil	Ones in a day
3	Takradhara	Ones in a day
4	Psora kot oientment	At night

Table 5: Showing mode of action of drug.

Sr.No	Dravya	Action
1.	<i>Ras manikya</i> ⁽⁵⁾	<i>vatshelshamak jwar nashak, kushtagna, swaskas-nashak</i>
2.	<i>Talsindur</i> ⁽⁶⁾	<i>twak-rakta vikar nashak , vishamjwarnashak</i>

3.	<i>Nimba</i> ⁽⁷⁾	<i>ushna, Kaphahara, Vranaodhanakara, kushtagna</i>
4.	<i>prawal pachamrut</i> ⁽⁸⁾	<i>pittshamak, swaskasnashak</i>
5.	<i>kaishor gugulu</i> ⁽⁹⁾	<i>vatraktanashak, kushtagna, vrananashak</i>
6.	<i>kamdudha rasa</i> ⁽¹⁰⁾	<i>pittvikarnashak, raktadoshanashak, dahavikar nashak</i>

4. Discussion

Hetu seven

Aaharaja Hetu

Aahar is one of *trayopstmbha*, so it is one of the chief responsible factors in the production of the *kushta*.

Viruddha Ahara (incompatible or antagonistic diet) ⁽¹¹⁾ Acharya *Charaka* has stated that the substances acting antagonistic to ‘*Dehadhatu*’ are *Vairodhika*. Acharya *Charaka* described eighteen types of *Viruddha Ahara* in *vimanstan*.

Mithya-Ahara (irregular Diet) ⁽¹²⁾

Viharaja Hetu. ⁽¹³⁾

Viharaja Hetu also play an important role in the production of *kushta*. *Mithya Vihara, Vegadharana & Panchakarma pacharanare* included in *Vihara Hetus*.

Mithya Vihara (irregularity in daily routine). The activities opposite to ‘*Svasthanavritta*’ is called ‘*Mithya Vihara*’. Sudden changes from cold to heat & vice-versa comes under in *Mithya Vihara*. *Vega Vidharana* – suppression of natural urges. ⁽¹⁴⁾

Krimi: ^(15,16)

Mahrshi charak and *sushrut* both mentioned *Krimi* is one of the probable causative factor for *kushta*.

Samprapti (Pathogenesis) ⁽¹⁷⁾

Most of the Acharyas have described the common *Samprapati* of the disease *Kushta* but they haven’t emphasized on the *Samprapti* of the *kushta*.

Samprati-Ghatak

- *Dosha– vata kapha dosha prakop*
- *Dushya – ras,rakta,mansa,lasika*
- *Srotas – rasavaha,raktavaha,mansavaha*
- *Srotodusti – sanchaya vrutti*
- *Udhhavasthana – twak,mansa*
- *Vyaktasthana – ubhay pradeshi*

5. Discussion

Discussion on treatment principles adopted w.r.t clinical condition

In line of treatment we think about *Aampachn, dipan,,vata kapha shamanaand shodhan chikitsa.*

- *rasmanikya, talsindhur* having properties of raktadushtinashak and kushtagna as well as praval panchamrut are pittshamak so reduces the symptomp of kandu of patient .
- Nimba having antibacterial,kushtaghna property as well as katukrohini and patol having katu tikta rasa which reduces the raktdushti kamdudha act as a pittshamak which is also helpful for reducing raktdoshti.
- *Stanik abhyanga* with *Valyapladi* oil reduces the *twakrkshata*
- Daily *virechana* by *trivruttavaleha* is helpful reducing pitta kaphaj *drushti* which is helps to decreases all the symptoms of the diseases.
- Psora kot having kushtagna drwya like swetakutaj, nimba,kirat-tikta as well as takradhara is vatkaphagna properties helps to reduces *twakvaivarnya*
- At the end of 2 months, there is improvement of 80% of total symptoms of the patient

6. Observation and Result

The results observed after the treatment: Improvement in signs and symptoms of the patient. Relief was found in kandu, (itching) twak vaivarnya (discolouration over skin),

Table 6: showing symptoms before and after treatment

No.	CHIEF COMPLAINTS	before treatment	after treatment
1	Ubhay pad & padtal pradeshi twakvaivarnya (discolouratio)	+++	+
2	Yanamasyoshaklopamam (erythmatous patches rounded and irregular shape appearing as silvery scale)	+++	–
3	Kandu (itching)	+++	–
4	twakrukshata (dryness)	++	–

7. Conclusion

Ayurvedic herbs along with *panchkarma* therapy shows highly significant results in ek-kushta.

Before Treatment

After Treatment

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